

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 DOMAIN INTRODUCTION

INTERNET OF THINGS

The Internet of things (IOT) is the network of everyday objects — physical things embedded with electronics, software, sensors, and connectivity enabling data exchange. Basically, a little networked computer is attached to a thing, allowing information exchange to and from that thing. Be it light bulbs, toasters, refrigerators, flower pots, watches, fans, planes, trains, automobiles, or anything else around you, a little networked computer can be combined with it to accept input (especially object control) or to gather and generate informational output (typically object status or other sensory data). This means computers will be permeating everything around us - ubiquitous embedded computing devices, uniquely identifiable, interconnected across the Internet. Because of low-cost, networkable microcontroller modules, the Internet of things is really starting to take off.

Espresso's ESP8266EX delivers highly integrated Wi-Fi SoC solution to meet users' continuous demands for efficient power usage, compact design and reliable performance in the Internet of Things industry. With the complete and self-contained Wi-Fi networking capabilities, ESP8266EX can perform either as a standalone application or as the slave to a host MCU. When ESP8266EX hosts the application, it promptly boots up from the flash. The integrated high speed cache helps to increase the system performance and optimize the system memory. Also, ESP8266EX can be applied to any microcontroller design as a Wi-Fi adaptor through SPI / SDIO or I2C / UART interfaces. ESP8266EX

integrates antenna switches, RF balun, power amplifier, low noise receive amplifier, filters and power management modules.

The compact design minimizes the PCB size and requires minimal external circuitries. Besides the Wi-Fi functionalities, ESP8266EX also integrates an enhanced version of Tensilica's L106 Diamond series 32-bit processor and on-chip SRAM. It can be interfaced with external sensors and other devices through the GPIOs. Software Development Kit (SDK) provides sample codes for various applications.

Espressif Systems' Smart Connectivity Platform (ESCP) enables sophisticated features including fast switch between sleep and wakeup mode for energy-efficient purpose, adaptive radio biasing for low-power operation, advance signal processing, spur cancellation and radio co-existence mechanisms for common cellular, Bluetooth, DDR, LVDS, LCD interference mitigation.

1.2 PROJECT DEFINITION

The EEG signals are fetched as fundamental input for muscle stimulation. Here EEG signals of the paralyzed person are fetched by sensor and processed to control muscular stimulation. If any abnormal values are detected in these features, an alert will be sent through IOT to physician.

1.3 PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Functional Electrical Stimulation (FES) is a rehabilitative technology that uses electrical currents applied to the peripheral nerves. When a stimulating current, consisting from a series of rectangular monophasic or biphasic (symmetrical or asymmetrical) electric pulses, is applied to the electrodes placed on the skin overlaying sensory-motor nerve structures, an electric field is established between two electrodes and ions will create a current in the tissue.

The ionic flow across the nerve influences the transmembrane potential and can generate an action potential. The action potential propagates along the nerve causing contraction of a paralyzed muscle.

In this way FES provides restoration of walking or arm movements in a person with complete or incomplete spinal cord injury, stroke or other lesions to the upper motor neuron. Surface stimulation electrode is a terminal through which electrical current passes into the underlying tissue. At the electrode-tissue interface a conversion occurs between the current of electrons driven through the wires coupled to the stimulator and the current of ions in the tissue. An electrode is usually made of metal. However, it may be made of a non-metal, commonly carbon.

The design criteria for surface stimulation electrodes are as follows: physical comfort to the skin, sufficient electrical surface area preventing skin irritation, use of hypo-allergenic materials, flexibility to follow body surface, ease of attachment and ability to remain in position for the duration of at least one active day, reusable, low cost, reliable means of connection to stimulator, resistant to medical solvents and electrode gels, low and stable electrical resistance. In this project, we are developing an EEG based muscle stimulation to paralysis people.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

Paper 1: Controlling a robot with extraocular muscles using EEG device

Authors: Cağatay Demirel, Hasan Kandemir.

This paper proposes a system to control the motion of a robot with the extraocular muscles using Mindwave Neurosky EEG Headset, which has one channel (two electrodes). Extraocular muscles are six muscles that control the movement of the eye and one muscle that controls the eyelid elevation. The electrophysiological signals are consumed from the FP1 sensor location of the brain to analyze the extraocular muscle actions. Two approaches are proposed for the recognition of these actions; a rule based recognition and a novel, learning based recognition approach. Using these approaches the speed and motion of a Sphero 2.0 robot is controlled, and the results are presented.

Paper 2: Embedded System based Autonavigation platform for Paralyzed people.

Authors: Rajesh Kannan Megalingam, Ananthakrishnan Ponnileth.

The stroke and spinal cord injury patients, elders and physically challenged who are affected by higher degree of disability such as quadriplegia, are not able to extensively use the powered wheelchairs for long periods of time. The major reason is that they are not able to provide the continuous physical effort required to guide the powered wheelchair which has joystick control mechanism as a standard control interface. An automated powered wheelchair can solve several problems. In this proposed automated system, the user does not have to continuously provide input. This substantially reduces the physical effort to guide the wheelchair and will be quite beneficial for quadriplegics. In addition the system does not use GPS, or any other wireless devices to determine the position of the wheelchair. This way, the system's cost can be reduced without compromising in accuracy. The reduced cost can increase the popularity of this system among individuals who belong to middle class families, especially in developing countries like India.

Paper 3: Brain-Computer Interface based home automation system for paralyzed people

Authors: Desai Pratikkumar Bhembhai, Garde Deval Sanjay.

Paralysis is the loss of ability to move some or all of the body. It is difficult for the paralysis people to live an independent life. Most of the recent research in smart-health care are focused on innovating technologies that could be used by individuals who are affected by this problem. In this paper a BCI based home controlling system has been proposed. The proposed system locates the position and orientation of the individual and hence identify the devices the user is targeting. User attention is captured using BCI module, which is further processed to identify the action. Proof of concept of the proposed approach was implemented. The experiments performed demonstrate that the proposed system could accurately identify the target device and hence could control the device.

Paper 4: Comparison Between Integrated Circuit and Transistor Pulse Generators for Functional Electrical Stimulation.

Authors : Jongsook Sanguantrakul, Yodchanan Wongsawat.

The purpose of this work was to contribute the pulse generator for the homemade functional electrical stimulation (FES) design with the practical use for basic rehabilitation and assistive devices such as limb activation or advanced usages such as stroke and spinal cord injury (SCI) patient based on brain damage. The proposed FES system consists of four sections, i.e. pulse generator, the voltage generator, H-bridge, and stimulation part. A self-adhesive electrode with carbon conductive was suggested for stimulation pad. The dependability and performance of the proposed pulse generator and FES circuit will be investigated. Nevertheless, the long stimulating time can provoke the muscle fatigue. This situation is not apparently related to stimulating waveform pattern and circuit board design that still need to be further examined.

Paper 5: Assitive Exoskeleton for paralyzed people.

Authors: Jubaer Islam Khan, K.M. Moshiur Rahman Songlap, Al Mamun Mizan.

This project represents the design of an exoskeleton robotic technology to assist the paralyzed people to move on their own, by supporting them physically and move their leg independently like a human leg. The working prototype has been designed of two features, one is support and the second one is motion with the help of Arduino based micro-controller support. In support part the robot is holding the whole physique of the paralyzed person and keep the person stand with support. The motion part is taking decision whether to sit down, stand up and walk based on the manual switch that will give command to the microcontroller which assess the command, and move the exoskeleton based on it. The prototype is developed with the intention to help the paralyzed people for helping them walk and remove them from the entitlement of disability.

CHAPTER 3

SYSTEM ANALYSIS

3.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

In existing days paralyzed people need FES cycle or assistance for performing exercises or stimulation to recover the paralyzed muscles and only healing assistance are provided based on scheduled period. There is no automated system for providing stimulation whenever the patient need. To overcome this is issue, we are going for proposed system.

3.1.1 DISADVANTAGES

- A paralyzed people need assistance for performing exercises or stimulation to recover.
- Economically the cost was high.

3.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

For paralyzed patients, even the limbs do not function properly, brain won't get affected. In the proposed system, these EEG signals are fetched as fundamental input for muscle stimulation. Here EEG signals of the paralyzed person are fetched by sensor and processed to control muscular stimulation. Along with gathering EEG signals, heart rate and respiratory level are also monitored. If any abnormal values are detected in these features, an alert will be sent through IoT to physician.

3.2.1 ADVANTAGES

- Without help of others the individual can stimulate muscle.
- Fast recovery from paralyzed part.

3.3 FEASIBILITY STUDY

3.3.1 TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY

The technical feasibility assessment is focused on gaining an understanding of the present technical resources of the organization and their applicability to the expected need of the proposed system. It is an evaluation of the hardware and software and how it meets the need of the proposed system.

3.3.1 OPERATIONAL FEASIBILITY

Operational feasibility is a measure of how well a proposed system solves the problems, and takes advantage of the opportunities identified during scope definition and how it satisfies the requirements identified in the requirements analysis phase of system development.

The operational feasibility assessment focuses on the degree to which the proposed developments project fits in with the existing business environment and objectives with regard to development schedule, delivery date, corporate culture, and existing business processes.

3.3.3 ECONOMIC FEASIBILITY

The purpose of the economic feasibility assessment is to determine the positive economic benefits to the organization that the proposed system will provide. It includes quantification and identification of all the benefits expected. This assessment typically involves a cost/benefits analysis.

CHAPTER 4

SYSTEM DESIGN

4.1 ARCHITECTURE DIAGRAM

A system architecture is the conceptual design that define the structure and / or behavior of a system. An architecture description is a formal description of a system organized in a way that supports reasoning about the structural principle.

Fig 4.1: System Architecture

4.2 UML DIAGRAM

Design deals with the various UML [Unified Modeling Language] diagrams for the implementation of project. Design is a meaningful engineering representation of a thing that is to be built. Software design is a process through which the requirements are translated into representation of the software. Design is the place where quality is rendered in software engineering.

4.2.1 USE CASE DIAGRAM

A Use Case describes a sequence of actions that provide something of measurable value to an actor and is drawn as a horizontal ellipse.

Fig 4.2: Use Case Diagram

4.2.2 SEQUENCE DIAGRAM

A sequence diagram shows an interaction arranged in time sequence. It shows object participating in interaction by the message they exchange arranged in time sequence. Vertical dimension represent time and horizontal dimension represent object.

SEQUENCE DIAGRAM:

Fig 4.3: Sequence Diagram

4.2.3 CLASS DIAGRAM

Class diagram represents the object orientation of a system. A class diagram is drawn as rectangle box with three components separate by horizontal lines. The top compartment holds the class name and middle compartment holds the attribute and bottom compartment holds list of operations.

CLASS DIAGRAM:

Fig 4.4:Class Diagram

4.2.4 ACTIVITY DIAGRAM

An activity diagram is a variation or special case of a state machine in which the states or activity representing the performance of operation and transitions are triggered by the completion of operation.

ACTIVITY DIAGRAM:

Fig 4.5: Activity Diagram

4.3 DATA FLOW DIAGRAM

The **Data Flow Diagram (DFD)** is a graphical representation of the flow of data through an information system. It enables you to represent the process in your information system from the viewpoint of data.

LEVEL 0:

DFD LEVEL 1:

LEVEL 1:

DFD LEVEL 1:

LEVEL 2:

DFD LEVEL 2:

OVERALL DATA FLOW DIAGRAM:

LEVEL 3:

OVERALL DFD:

Figure 4.9: Level 3 of Data Flow Diagram

CHAPTER 5

SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

5.1 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

The hardware requirements may serve as the basis for a contract for the implementation of the system and should therefore be a complete and consistent specification of the whole system. They are used by software engineers as the starting point for the system design.

- MICROCONTROLLER
- POWER SUPPLY
- EEG SENSOR
- HEARTBEAT SENSOR
- RESPIRATORY SENSOR
- IOT MODULE
- VIBRATION MOTORS
- LCD

5.2 SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

- EMBEDDED C
- ARDUINO IDE

CHAPTER 6

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

6.1 SOFTWARE DESCRIPTION

6.1.1 EMBEDDED C

High-level language programming has long been in use for embedded-systems development. However, assembly programming still prevails, particularly for digital-signal processor (DSP) based systems. DSPs are often programmed in assembly language by programmers who know the processor architecture inside out. The key motivation for this practice is performance, despite the disadvantages of assembly programming when compared to high-level language programming.

If the video decoding takes 80 percent of the CPU-cycle budget instead of 90 percent, for instance, there are twice as many cycles available for audio processing. This coupling of performance to end-user features is characteristic of many of the real-time applications in which DSP processors are applied. DSPs have a highly specialized architecture to achieve the performance requirements for signal processing applications within the limits of cost and power consumption set for consumer applications. Unlike a conventional Load-Store (RISC) architecture, DSPs have a data path with memory-access units that directly feed into the arithmetic units. Address registers are taken out of the general-purpose register file and placed next to the memory units in a separate register file.

A further specialization of the data path is the coupling of multiplication and addition to form a single cycle Multiply-accumulate unit (MAC). It is combined with special-purpose accumulator registers, which are separate from the general-purpose registers. Data memory is segmented and

placed close to the MAC to achieve the high bandwidths required to keep up with the streamlined data path. Limits are often placed on the extent of memory-addressing operations. The localization of resources in the data path saves many data movements that typically take place in a Load-Store architecture.

The most important, common arithmetic extension to DSP architectures is the handling of saturated fixed-point operations by the arithmetic unit. Fixed-point arithmetic can be implemented with little additional cost over integer arithmetic. Automatic saturation (or clipping) significantly reduces the number of control-flow instructions needed for checking overflow explicitly in the program. Changes in technological and economic requirements make it more expensive to continue programming DSPs in assembly. Staying with the mobile phone as an example, the signal-processing algorithms required become increasingly complex. Features such as stronger error correction and encryption must be added. Communication protocols become more sophisticated and require much more code to implement. In certain markets, multiple protocol stacks are implemented to be compatible with multiple service providers. In addition, backward compatibility with older protocols is needed to stay synchronized with provider networks that are in a slow process of upgrading.

Today, most embedded processors are offered with C compilers. Despite this, programming DSPs is still done in assembly for the signal processing parts or, at best, by using assembly-written libraries supplied by manufacturers. The key reason for this is that although the architecture is well matched to the requirements of the signal-processing application, there is no way to express the algorithms efficiently and in a natural way in Standard C. Saturated arithmetic.

Embedded C is designed to bridge the performance mismatch between Standard C and the embedded hardware and application architecture. It extends the C language with the primitives that are needed by signal-processing applications and that are commonly provided by DSP processors. The design of the support for fixed-point data types and named address spaces in Embedded C is based on DSP-C. DSP-C [1] is an industry-designed extension of C with which experience was gained since 1998 by various DSP manufacturers in their compilers. For the development of DSP-C by ACE (the company three of us work for), cooperation was sought with embedded-application designers and DSP manufacturers.

The Embedded C specification extends the C language to support freestanding embedded processors in exploiting the multiple address space functionality, user-defined named address spaces, and direct access to processor and I/O registers. These features are common for the small, embedded processors used in most consumer products. The features introduced by Embedded C are fixed-point and saturated arithmetic, segmented memory spaces, and hardware I/O addressing. The description we present here addresses the extensions from a language-design perspective, as opposed to the programmer or processor architecture perspective.

6.2 MODULES DESCRIPTION

- Human-Computer interaction.
- Monitoring the values.
- Muscle stimulation.
- Indicates abnormal message through IOT.
- Emergency response.

6.2.1 Human-Computer Interaction

EEG Sensor is the world's least expensive research-grade EEG headset available. Designed for interface with mobile devices (IOS and Android) and desktop (Win and Mac), it can be used with a wide variety of games, brain training and education applications. Its clear brainwave signal is based on the TGAM, the bio-sensor chipset that revolutionized an industry. It is an excellent introduction into the world of brain-computer interface (BCI). The device consists of a headset, an ear-clip, and a sensor arm. The headset's reference and ground electrodes are on the ear clip and the EEG electrode is on the sensor arm, resting on the forehead above the eye (FP1 position). It uses a single AAA battery with 8 hours of battery life

Electroencephalogram (EEG) sensors require conductive gel to ensure low impedance electrical contact between the sensor and skin. We present a gel-free, non-contact EEG sensor with on-board electrode those capacitive couples to the skin. Active shielding of the high-impedance input significantly reduces noise pickup, and reduces variations in gain. The measured input-referred noise, over 1- 100 Hz frequency range, is $2\mu\text{vrms}$ at 0.2mm sensor distance, and $17\mu\text{vrms}$ at 3.2mm distance. Experiments coupling the sensor to human scalp through hair and to chest through clothing produce clear EEG recorded Signals.

6.2.2 Monitoring the values

LCD stands for liquid crystal display. They come in many sizes 8x1 , 8x2 , 10x2 , 16x1 , 16x2 , 16x4 , 20x2 , 20x4 ,24x2 , 30x2 , 32x2 , 40x2 etc . Many multinational companies like Philips Hitachi Panasonic make their own special kind of LCD'S to be used in their products. All the LCD'S performs the

same functions (display characters numbers special characters ASCII characters etc). Their programming is also same and they all have same 14 pins (0-13) or 16 pins (0 to 15). Alphanumeric displays are used in a wide range of applications, including palmtop computers, word processors, photocopiers, point of sale terminals, medical instruments, cellular phones, etc.

This is an LCD Display designed for E-blocks. It is a 16 character, 2-line alphanumeric LCD display connected to a single 9-way D-type connector. This allows the device to be connected to most E-Block I/O ports. The LCD display requires data in a serial format, which is detailed in the user guide below. The display also requires a 5V power supply. Please take care not to exceed 5V, as this will cause damage to the device. The 5V is best generated from the E-blocks Multi programmer or a 5V fixed regulated power supply. The 16 x 2 intelligent alphanumeric dot matrix displays is capable of displaying 224 different characters and symbols. A full list of the characters and symbols is printed on pages 7/8 (note these symbols can vary between brand of LCD used). This booklet provides all the technical specifications for connecting the unit, which requires a single power supply (+5V).

6.2.3 Muscle Stimulation

A vibration motor! This shaft less vibratory motor is perfect for non-audible indicators. Use in any number of applications to indicate to the wearer when a status has changed. All moving parts are protected within the housing. With a 2- 3.6V operating range, these units shake crazily at 3V. Once anchored to a PCB or within a pocket, the unit vibrates softly but notice ably. This high quality unit comes with a 3M adhesive backing and reinforced connection wires. There are two basic types of vibration motor. An eccentric rotating mass vibration motor (ERM) uses a small unbalanced mass on a DC motor, when it rotates it creates a force that translates to vibrations. A linear resonant actuator

(LRA) contains a small internal mass attached to a spring, which creates a force when driven.

Vibration motor is a compact size coreless DC motor used to inform the users of receiving the signal by vibrating, no sound. The cylinder shape is also called bar type vibration motor. This vibrating motor is essentially a motor that is improperly balanced. This unbalanced force displaces the motor. Its high speed displacement makes the motor to wobble, which is known as the vibrating. As specialists in the supply and design of vibration motors, you can find our stocked motors in our product catalogue. If you can't find exactly what you need, or would like to discuss a project, please do not hesitate to contact our engineers here.

6.2.4 Indicates Abnormal Message Through IOT

The Internet of things (IOT) is the network of everyday objects — physical things embedded with electronics, software, sensors, and connectivity enabling data exchange. Basically, a little networked computer is attached to a thing, allowing information exchange to and from that thing. Be it light bulbs, toasters, refrigerators, flower pots, watches, fans, planes, trains, automobiles, or anything else around you, a little networked computer can be combined with it to accept input (especially object control) or to gather and generate informational output (typically object status or other sensory data). This means computers will be permeating everything around us - ubiquitous embedded computing devices, uniquely identifiable, interconnected across the Internet. Because of low-cost, networkable microcontroller modules, the Internet of things is really starting to take off.

6.2.5 Emergency Response

After the alert message were received to doctor. the emergency response were be taken.

CHAPTER 7

SYSTEM TESTING

7.1 TESTING OBJECTIVES

Testing is a set of activities that can be planned in advance and conducted systematically. For this reason a template for software testing, a set of steps into which we can place specific test case design techniques and testing methods should be defined for software process. The software, which has been developed, has to be tested to prove its validity. Testing is considered to be the least creative phase of the whole cycle of system design. Testing often accounts for more effort than any other software engineering activity. If it is conducted haphazardly, time is wasted, unnecessary effort is expended, and even worse, errors sneak through undetected, it would therefore seem reasonable to establish a systematic strategy for testing software.

Type of Testing

There are two type of testing according their behaviors

1. Unconventional Testing
2. Conventional Testing

Unconventional Testing

Unconventional testing is a process of verification which is doing by SQA (Software Quality Assurance) team. It is a prevention technique which is performing from beginning to ending of the project development. In this process SQA team verifies project development activities and insuring that developing project is fulfilling the requirement of the client or not.

Conventional Testing

Conventional Testing is a process of finding the bugs and validating the project. Testing team involves in this testing process and validating that developed project is according to client requirement or not. This process is a correction technique where testing team find bugs and reporting to the development team for developed project built.

7.2 TEST CASE DESIGN

7.2.1 Unit Testing

Unit testing involves the design of test cases that validate that the internal program logic is functioning properly, and that program input produce valid outputs. All decision branches and internal code flow should be validated. It is the testing of individual software units of the application it is done after the completion of an individual unit before integration. This is a structural testing, that relies on knowledge of its construction and is invasive. Unit tests perform basic tests at component level and test a specific business process, application, and/or system configuration. Unit tests ensure that each unique path of a business process performs accurately to the documented specifications and contains clearly defined inputs and expected results.

7.2.2 Functional Testing

Functional tests provide systematic demonstrations that functions tested are available as specified by the business and technical requirements, system documentation, and user manuals. Functional testing is centered on the following items.

7.2.3 System Testing

System testing ensures that the entire integrated software system meets requirements. It tests a configuration to ensure known and predictable results, An example of system testing is the configuration oriented system integration test System testing is based on process descriptions and flows, emphasizing pre-driven process links and integration points.

7.2.4 Acceptance Testing

User Acceptance Testing is a critical phase of any project and requires significant participation by the end user. It also ensures that the system meets the functional requirements.

Acceptance testing for Data Synchronization:

- The Acknowledgements will be received by the Sender Node after the Packets are received by the Destination Node.

- The Route add operation is done only when there is a Route request in need.

- The Status of Nodes information is done automatically in the Cache Updation process.

7.3 TEST CASE RESULT:

Test	Test Requirement	Action /Input	Expected Result	Actual Result	Pass/Fail
1	Recording brain activity	Monitoring/ EEG sensor	Monitoring abnormalities of brain	Activity of the brain recorded	Pass
2	Finding heart rate	Heart beat detection/Heart Beat sensor	Measures the change in volume of blood	Heart rate detected	pass
3	Detecting respiratory rate	Respiratory rate detection/ Respiratory sensor	Expansion of chest during breath volume detection	Respiratory Rate of flow of breath per unit	Pass
4	Conversion of waveform	Analog to digital conversion/ waveform of recorded value	Analog to digital converted value	Digital form of recorded value	Pass
5	Proceeding activity process	Motor processing/ recorded value	Motor starts when value reach its range	Processing of Initial stimulation process	Pass

Fig 7.1: Test Case Result

CHAPTER 8

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

8.1 TEST CASE RESULTS

The EEG signals are fetched as fundamental input for muscle stimulation. Here EEG signals of the paralyzed person are fetched by sensor and processed to control muscular stimulation. Along with gathering EEG signals, heart rate and respiratory level are also monitored. If any abnormal values are detected in these features, an alert will be sent through IOT to physician.

WEB SERVER : Controlling Section

CHAPTER 9

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

9.1 CONCLUSION

In this paper, for paralyzed patients, the EEG signals are fetched as fundamental input for muscle stimulation. Here EEG signals of the paralyzed person are fetched by sensor and processed to control muscular stimulation. Along with gathering EEG signals, heart rate and respiratory level are also monitored. If any abnormal values are detected in these features, an alert will be sent through IoT to physician.

9.2 FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

In present, for human hard to detect the accurate sense of the brain activity. So in future the technology were be improved and new way of solution were be discover to detect the accurate brain activity.

APPENDICES

A.SOURCE CODE:

```
/*
```

```
  AnalogReadSerial
```

```
  Reads an analog input on pin 0, prints the result to the Serial Monitor.
```

```
  Graphical representation is available using Serial Plotter (Tools > Serial Plotter menu).
```

```
  Attach the center pin of a potentiometer to pin A0, and the outside pins to +5V and ground.
```

```
  This example code is in the public domain.
```

```
  http://www.arduino.cc/en/Tutorial/AnalogReadSerial
```

```
*/
```

```
// the setup routine runs once when you press reset:
```

```
#include <LiquidCrystal.h>
```

```
LiquidCrystal lcd(13, 12, 11, 10, 9, 8);
```

```
int d1 = 2;
```

```
int d2 = 3;
```

```
int d3 = 4;
```

```
int e=0,l=0;
```

```
int h=0,g=0,a=0,x,count1,v;
```

```
int res=0;
```

```
void setup() {
```

```
  // initialize serial communication at 9600 bits per second:
```

```
  Serial.begin(9600);
```

```
    pinMode(d1, OUTPUT);
```

```
  pinMode(d2, OUTPUT);
```

```
  pinMode(d3, OUTPUT);
```

```
  lcd.begin(16, 2);
```

```

    lcd.setCursor(2, 0);
    lcd.print(" EEG_BASED ");
    lcd.setCursor(0, 1);
    lcd.print("MUSCLE_STIMULATOR");
    delay(2000);
    lcd.clear();
}
int count=0;
int data;
int z[10];
int i=0;
int d=0;
// the loop routine runs over and over again forever:
//a[i]=0;
void loop() {
    // read the input on analog pin 0:
    for(i=1;i<10;i++)
    {
res = analogRead(A0);
        hb();
        lcd.setCursor(0, 0);
        lcd.print("HB:");
            lcd.print(h);
            lcd.print(" ");
        lcd.setCursor(8, 0);
        lcd.print("RES:");
            lcd.print(res);
            lcd.print(" ");
    }
}

```

```

    lcd.setCursor(13, 1);
    lcd.print("C:");
    lcd.print(count1);
    z[i] = analogRead(A3);
    //Serial.println("-----COLLECTING :EEG: SAMPLES-----");
    d= z[i]-z[i-1];
    // if((d==1)||(d==0))
        if((d==1)&&(z[i]<800))
    {
        count1++;
    }
    Serial.print("z[0]=");
    Serial.print(z[i-1]);
    Serial.print(" z[1]=");
    Serial.print(z[i]);
    Serial.print("count=");
    Serial.print(count1);
    Serial.print(" d=");
    Serial.print(d);
    Serial.print(" i=");
    Serial.println(i);
    delay(300);
    if(i==9)
    {
        i=1;
    }
    health();
    if(a==1)
    {

```

```

health();
  lcd.setCursor(0, 1);
  lcd.print("MUS_ST:");
  lcd.print("ACTIVE");
  digitalWrite(d1, HIGH);
  digitalWrite(d2, HIGH);
  digitalWrite(d3, HIGH);
  delay(5000);
  a=0;
  l=0;

}
if(a==0)
{
  // health();
  lcd.setCursor(0, 1);
  lcd.print("MUS_ST:");
  lcd.print("SLEEP ");
  digitalWrite(d1, LOW);
  digitalWrite(d2, LOW);
  digitalWrite(d3, LOW);
}
if((count1>=2)&&(z[i]<900))
{
  Serial.print("EEG DATAS=");
  Serial.println(z[i]);
  a=1;
  count1=0;
}

```

```

    }
    }
void hb()
{
    int hr = analogRead(A1);

    // Serial.print(hr);
    if((hr>900)&&(hr<1005))
    {
        h= 70+1;
        h=h;
        {
            count++;
        }
        if(x==0)
        {
            count=0;
        }
        if(count>=6)
        {
            x=0;
            v=1;
        }
    }
    if((hr>800)&&(hr<900))
    {
        h= 70+3;
        h=h;
    }
}

```

```
}
if((hr>700)&&(hr<800))
{
h= 70+6;
h=h;
{
count++;
}
if(x==0)
{
count=0;
}
if(count>=6)
{
x=0;
v=1;
}
}
if((hr>600)&&(hr<700))
{
h= 71;
h=h;
}
if((hr>300)&&(hr<400))
{
h= 74+1;
h=h;
}
```

```

if((hr>200)&&(hr<300))
{
h= 72+5;
h=h;
{
count++;
}
if(x==0)
{
count=0;
}
if(count>=6)
{
x=0;
v=1;
}
}
if((hr>500)&&(hr<600))
{
h=0;
}
}
//void eeg()
//{
// int eegd = analogRead(A3);
// Serial.print("eeg=");
// Serial.println(eegd);
////if((eegd>680)&&(eegd<800))
////{

```

```

//// g++;
////}
////
////if(g>5)
////{
////  Serial.println("stimulation");
////  g=0;
////a=1;
////
////}
//
//if(eegd>960)
//{
//  e++;
//
//}
//
//
//if(eegd<=900)
//{
//  e=0;
//}
//
//if((e>10)&&(eegd>979))////////////////////////////////////
//{
//
//  l++;
//
//}

```

```

//
//if(l>4)////////////////////////////////////
//{
// a=1;
//}
// if(a==1)
// {
// // health();
// lcd.setCursor(0, 1);
// lcd.print("MUS_ST:");
// lcd.print("ACTIVE");
// digitalWrite(d1, HIGH);
// digitalWrite(d2, HIGH);
// digitalWrite(d3, HIGH);
// delay(5000);
// a=0;
// l=0;
//
// }
// if(a==0)
// {
// // health();
// lcd.setCursor(0, 1);
// lcd.print("MUS_ST:");
// lcd.print("SLEEP ");
// digitalWrite(d1, LOW);
// digitalWrite(d2, LOW);
// digitalWrite(d3, LOW);
// }

```

```

//
//
//}
void health()
{
String Str="";
Str+="sensornewgsm.php?client=iot2k19067&s1=";
Str+=res;
if(res>500)
{
Str+="&s2=ABNORMAL";
}
if(res<=500)
{
Str+="&s2=NORMAL";
}
Str+="&s3=";
Str+=h+1;
if(h<3)
{
Str+="&s4=ABNORMAL";
}
if(h>3)
{
Str+="&s4=NORMAL";
}

if(a==1)

```

```
{  
  Str+="&s5=ACTIVE";  
  Str+="&sms=YES&msg=ACTIVE#";  
  
}  
if(a==0)  
{  
  Str+="&s5=SLEEP";  
  
  Str+="&sms=NO&msg=NA#";  
  
}  
Serial.print(Str);  
  delay(300);  
}
```

B.SCREENSHOTS:

Arduino Setup Installation

Choose the component to install

Choose the installation directory

Boot Download steps

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